

Facile synthesis of CuO nanoparticles loaded activated carbon from cashew nut shells for enhanced photocatalytic degradation of Methylene Blue dye

B. Veeramani¹. K.Raghu^{1*}

¹Department of Physics, Annamalai University, Chidambaram, Tamil Nadu, 608 002.
INDIA

²Department of Physics, Arignar Anna Arts and Science college, Villupuram, Tamil Nadu,
605 602. INDIA

Received: Sep 7, 2025

Accepted: Nov 4, 2025

Published: Nov 6, 2025

Abstract

In this study, activated carbon (AC) derived from cashew nut shells was used as a support for copper oxide (CuO) nanoparticles to form an AC–CuO nanocomposite. XRD confirmed the crystalline nature of CuO with an average crystallite size of about 16 nm. FTIR spectra showed characteristic CuO vibrations and surface functional groups, indicating successful bonding between CuO and AC. HRTEM images revealed uniformly dispersed CuO nanoparticles with distinct lattice fringes, confirming nanoscale crystallinity. BET analysis showed a high surface area and mesoporous structure suitable for adsorption and photocatalytic activity. Zeta potential measurements indicated a negative surface charge, enhancing colloidal stability and interaction with methylene blue dye molecules. TGA analysis demonstrated improved thermal stability compared with pure activated carbon. UV–Visible spectra displayed strong absorption in the UV–visible region, confirming its photocatalytic potential. The nanocomposite achieved 92% degradation of methylene blue within 90 minutes following pseudo-second-order kinetics ($R^2 = 0.9952$). The catalyst retained 92% efficiency after five cycles, proving excellent stability, reusability, and suitability for wastewater treatment applications.

Keywords: CuO, Cashew nut shell, and Methylene blue.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of industrialization and urbanization has resulted in the widespread discharge of synthetic dyes into aquatic environments. Among these pollutants, methylene blue (MB), a cationic dye widely used in the textile, paper, and leather industries, has attracted significant attention due to its persistence, non-biodegradability, and potential toxicity to living organisms [1]. Even at low concentrations, MB imparts intense coloration to

water, reducing light penetration and disturbing aquatic ecosystems. Furthermore, its prolonged exposure can cause harmful effects such as eye irritation, nausea, and respiratory distress in humans. Conventional wastewater treatment methods, including adsorption, coagulation–flocculation, and biological degradation, often prove ineffective in completely removing MB due to its stable aromatic structure and high solubility [2]. These limitations have prompted the exploration of advanced treatment technologies that are not only efficient but also environmentally sustainable [3].

Photocatalysis has emerged as a promising technique for the degradation of organic pollutants, offering the advantages of complete mineralization, reduced secondary pollution, and the use of solar energy as a renewable driving force. Semiconductor metal oxides such as TiO₂, ZnO, and CuO have been extensively investigated as photocatalysts because of their strong light absorption, stability, and ability to generate electron–hole pairs under irradiation [4]. Among these, copper oxide (CuO), a p-type semiconductor with a narrow band gap (~1.2–1.7 eV), has attracted increasing attention for visible-light-driven photocatalysis [5]. CuO nanoparticles exhibit excellent electrical conductivity, chemical stability, and catalytic properties, making them highly suitable for wastewater treatment applications. However, challenges such as particle agglomeration, limited surface area, and rapid recombination of photogenerated electron–hole pairs restrict the standalone efficiency of CuO as a photocatalyst [6]. To overcome these limitations, researchers have explored the use of supports or composite materials to stabilize CuO nanoparticles and enhance their photocatalytic performance [7].

Activated carbon (AC) is particularly appealing in this regard due to its high surface area, tunable porosity, and ability to adsorb organic pollutants. By serving as a host matrix, AC not only prevents nanoparticle aggregation but also provides abundant surface-active sites for pollutant adsorption and subsequent degradation [8]. Moreover, its high electrical conductivity facilitates charge transfer, suppressing electron–hole recombination and thereby improving photocatalytic efficiency. Thus, coupling CuO nanoparticles with activated carbon offers a synergistic effect that combines the adsorption capacity of AC with the photocatalytic activity of CuO [9]. Traditionally, activated carbon is prepared from petroleum-based or expensive precursors, raising concerns regarding cost and environmental sustainability. In recent years, attention has shifted toward the utilization of agricultural and biomass wastes as renewable precursors for activated carbon production [10]. Cashew nut

shells (CNS), an abundant agro-waste byproduct of the cashew processing industry, have emerged as a promising raw material owing to their high carbon content, low cost, and natural availability in tropical countries [11]. Improper disposal of CNS often leads to environmental problems, while their valorization into activated carbon not only mitigates waste management issues but also supports circular economy practices. Activated carbon derived from CNS has been reported to exhibit well-developed porosity, high adsorption capacity, and abundant surface functionalities, making it an excellent candidate for supporting nanomaterials in catalytic applications.

Recent studies have highlighted the potential of biomass-derived activated carbon composites with metal oxide nanoparticles for environmental remediation. For example, ZnO/AC and TiO₂/AC composites have shown enhanced photocatalytic degradation of dyes compared to their pristine counterparts [12-13]. Similarly, CuO loaded onto biomass-derived AC has demonstrated improved activity due to the synergistic interaction between the semiconductor and the carbon support. However, there remains limited research on the use of cashew nut shell-derived activated carbon as a support for CuO nanoparticles, despite its advantageous properties and sustainable origin. In this context, the present study focuses on the facile synthesis of CuO nanoparticles loaded onto activated carbon derived from cashew nut shells and their application in the photocatalytic degradation of methylene blue dye. The approach not only provides a green and cost-effective route for nanocomposite preparation but also promotes waste-to-value conversion of agro-industrial residues [14]. By systematically characterizing the structural, morphological, optical, and surface properties of the synthesized AC–CuO nanocomposites, this work aims to establish their suitability as efficient photocatalysts for environmental remediation. The synergistic effect of CuO nanoparticles and CNS-derived activated carbon is expected to enhance adsorption, improve charge carrier separation, and facilitate effective degradation of MB under irradiation. Overall, this research addresses the dual challenge of managing agro-waste and mitigating dye pollution by developing a sustainable, high-performance photocatalyst. The study not only demonstrates the potential of cashew nut shells as an economical precursor for activated carbon but also contributes to the growing field of green nanotechnology for environmental applications.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 MATERIALS

Copper(II) nitrate trihydrate $[\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ sodium hydroxide (NaOH), and Methylene Blue (MB) dye were procured from reputable chemical suppliers. Cashew nut shells, sourced from local agricultural waste, were thoroughly cleaned to remove debris and impurities before processing. All reagents were of analytical grade and used without further purification.

2.1.1 Preparation of Activated Carbon from Cashew Nut Shells

Cashew nut shells used in this study were collected from Virudhachalam Taluk, located in the Cuddalore district of Tamil Nadu, India. The shells were thoroughly washed with deionized water to remove adhering dust, dirt, and organic residues. After cleaning, they were oven-dried at 110 °C for 24 hours to ensure complete removal of moisture. The dried shells were then ground and sieved to obtain particles smaller than 2 mm, which served as the raw material for activated carbon preparation.

Chemical activation was carried out using sodium hydroxide (NaOH) as the activating agent due to its effectiveness in enhancing the surface area and porosity of the carbon material. Methylene Blue (MB), a cationic dye with the molecular formula $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_3\text{SCl}$, was employed as a model pollutant to evaluate the adsorption efficiency of the synthesized activated carbon.

All reagents, including NaOH and hydrochloric acid (HCl), were of analytical grade ($\geq 99\%$ purity) and procured from SD Merck Fine Chemicals, India. The chemicals were used without further purification. Prior to use, all glassware was acid-washed, and only deionized water was utilized throughout the study to prevent contamination and ensure consistency during solution preparation and sample dilution.

2.1.2 Synthesis of CuO Nanoparticles on Activated Carbon

To synthesize CuO-loaded activated carbon, an aqueous solution of copper(II) nitrate trihydrate was added dropwise to a suspension of cashew nut shell-derived activated carbon under continuous stirring. Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was then added gradually to maintain a basic pH, promoting the precipitation of CuO nanoparticles. The resulting mixture was aged, filtered, and thoroughly washed with deionized water to remove residual impurities. The

obtained product was dried and subsequently calcined at 400 °C to achieve the formation of crystalline CuO nanoparticles uniformly distributed on the activated carbon surface.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 TGA / DTA analysis

Figure 1. TGA/DTA illustration of AC – CuO nanoparticles

The thermal behavior of the AC–CuO nanoparticles was investigated using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential thermal analysis (DTA), as presented in Figure 1. The TGA curve shows a multi-step weight loss pattern as the temperature increases from room temperature to 1000°C. The initial minor weight loss below 150 °C can be attributed to the evaporation of physically adsorbed water molecules and moisture present on the surface of the sample [15]. A sharp and significant weight loss is observed between 200–300 °C, which corresponds to the decomposition of organic functional groups and residual volatile matter present in the activated carbon matrix. This transition is supported by a strong exothermic peak in the DTA curve, suggesting the combustion of carbonaceous species and the release of trapped gases. Beyond 300 °C, a gradual and continuous weight loss is observed up to 800 °C, which can be associated with the slow degradation of more stable oxygen-containing groups (such as carboxyl, carbonyl, and phenolic groups) and partial structural rearrangements within the activated carbon [16]. The relatively stable profile above

800 °C indicates the thermal stability of the AC–CuO nanocomposite. The final residual weight confirms the presence of thermally stable CuO nanoparticles embedded within the carbon matrix, demonstrating their ability to withstand high temperatures without decomposition. The thermal stability of AC–CuO nanoparticles is significantly improved compared to pure activated carbon, as the CuO nanoparticles act as reinforcing agents that inhibit complete burnout of the carbon structure. This synergistic effect not only enhances thermal durability but also makes the material suitable for high-temperature applications. In addition, the strong exothermic feature observed in the DTA profile reflects the catalytic effect of CuO in promoting the oxidation of carbonaceous species, which is highly beneficial for photocatalytic and catalytic applications.

3.2 X –RAY DIFFRACTION ANALYSIS

Figure 2. XRD pattern of (a) Pure AC (Cashew Nut Shell) (b) AC – CuO nanoparticles

The X-ray diffraction patterns of the pure activated carbon (AC) derived from cashew nut shell and AC–CuO nanocomposite are shown in Figure 2(a) and 2(b), respectively. The broad diffraction hump observed in pure AC (Figure 1a) in the range of 20° – 30° (2θ) indicates the amorphous nature of the carbon structure. In contrast, the AC–CuO nanocomposite (Figure 1b) displays several sharp and intense diffraction peaks, confirming the successful incorporation and crystalline nature of CuO nanoparticles within

the carbon matrix. The prominent peaks at 2θ values of $\sim 32.5^\circ$, 35.6° , 38.8° , and 48.8° correspond to the (-110) , (002) , (-111) , (111) , (-202) , (-113) and (002) planes of monoclinic CuO, which are in good agreement with the JCPDS card No. 45-0937 [17]. The absence of any additional impurity peaks suggests that the synthesized CuO nanoparticles are phase pure. The average crystallite size of the CuO nanoparticles, calculated using the Debye–Scherrer equation [18] was found to be 16 nm, which confirms their nanocrystalline nature. Compared to chemically synthesized CuO nanoparticles reported in literature, the present biosynthesis approach using cashew nut shell–derived activated carbon not only produced smaller-sized particles but also offered improved crystallinity [19]. The carbon matrix derived from cashew nut shells plays a dual role: (i) acting as a reducing and stabilizing agent during the synthesis of CuO nanoparticles, and (ii) providing a high surface area support, which enhances the dispersion of nanoparticles and prevents agglomeration. This sustainable route thus demonstrates a green and low-cost alternative to conventional chemical synthesis. The incorporation of CuO nanoparticles into activated carbon significantly enhances its functional properties. In particular, the AC–CuO nanocomposite exhibits promising photocatalytic potential due to the synergistic effect between CuO and carbon. The high surface area of AC facilitates efficient adsorption of dye molecules, while the CuO nanoparticles promote photodegradation under visible light irradiation. This combined mechanism makes the material a suitable candidate for wastewater treatment applications, particularly in the removal of toxic organic dyes.

3.3 FTIR Analysis

Figure 3. FTIR spectrum of AC – CuO nanoparticles

Figure 3 displays the FTIR spectrum of AC–CuO nanoparticles, highlighting several distinct peaks. The broad bands at 3358 cm^{-1} and 3146 cm^{-1} are attributed to O–H stretching vibrations, indicating adsorbed water or hydroxyl groups on the nanoparticle surface [20]. Weak peaks at 1675 cm^{-1} and 1506 cm^{-1} correspond to C=O and C=C stretching vibrations, respectively, likely arising from carbonaceous material in the composite[21]. The prominent peak at 1061 cm^{-1} can be assigned to C–O stretching vibrations. Most notably, strong absorption bands at 807 cm^{-1} , 596 cm^{-1} , and 469 cm^{-1} are characteristic of Cu–O stretching, confirming the formation of copper oxide within the AC matrix[22]. The presence of O–H and C–O related vibrations demonstrates that the AC–CuO nanoparticles are functionalized with surface groups capable of facilitating interaction with water and organic molecules, which is beneficial for catalytic and adsorption processes. The sharp bands attributed to Cu–O vibrations ($807, 596, 469\text{ cm}^{-1}$) directly confirm the successful synthesis of the CuO phase, as these are in good agreement with literature values for monoclinic CuO. The observed carbonyl and aromatic C=C peaks ($1675, 1506\text{ cm}^{-1}$) suggest residual carbon functionalities from the activated carbon component, further enhancing the surface reactivity. Collectively, these spectral features indicate that the AC–CuO nanocomposite possesses a rich surface chemistry and robust CuO structure, supporting its suitability for photocatalytic and environmental applications.

3.4 UV – VISIBLE ANALYSIS

The optical properties of the AC–CuO nanoparticles were examined using UV–Visible spectroscopy, and the results are shown in Figure 4(a). The absorption spectrum exhibits a sharp and intense absorption peak centered at 293 nm, which corresponds to the electronic transition of CuO nanoparticles[23]. The strong absorption in the UV region indicates the formation of nanosized particles and quantum confinement effects[24]. The broad absorption tail towards the visible region further confirms the effective interaction between CuO nanoparticles and the activated carbon matrix, suggesting their potential for photocatalytic activity under solar irradiation.

Figure 4. (a) UV – Visible spectrum (b) band gap energy of AC – CuO nanoparticles

The optical band gap of the AC-CuO nanoparticles was determined using the Tauc relation $(\alpha h\nu)^2 = A(h\nu - E_g)$, where α is the absorption coefficient, $h\nu$ is the photon energy, and E_g is the band gap energy. The extrapolation of the linear region of the Tauc plot (Figure 4b) gives a band gap value of 4.0 eV. This relatively higher band gap compared to bulk CuO (~ 1.2 – 1.7 eV) can be attributed to the nanoscale size of the particles, which induces strong quantum confinement[25]. The presence of activated carbon plays a vital role in enhancing light absorption and charge separation. The porous structure of carbon increases the effective surface area, while its conductive nature facilitates electron transfer from the excited CuO

nanoparticles, thereby suppressing recombination of electron–hole pairs. This synergistic effect between AC and CuO not only tunes the optical properties but also improves the photocatalytic efficiency of the composite material for dye degradation and other environmental remediation applications.

3.5 ZETA POTENTIAL AND DLS ANALYSIS

Figure 5. (a) Zeta potential (b) DLS illustration of AC – CuO nanoparticles

The surface charge and stability of the AC–CuO nanoparticles were examined using zeta potential analysis (Figure 5a). The measured zeta potential value was -27 mV, which indicates that the nanoparticles carry a moderately high negative surface charge. Generally,

zeta potential values greater than ± 25 mV are considered to provide good electrostatic repulsion, thereby preventing particle aggregation[26]. Hence, the obtained value confirms that the AC–CuO nanoparticles exhibit appreciable colloidal stability in aqueous suspension. The negative surface charge originates from the adsorption of hydroxyl and oxygen-containing functional groups on the nanoparticle surface, which is further enhanced by the activated carbon matrix. Dynamic light scattering analysis was performed to determine the hydrodynamic particle size distribution of AC–CuO nanoparticles (Figure 5b). The histogram indicates a bimodal distribution with particle sizes mainly ranging between 20–35 nm, with a significant population around 28–30 nm. A small fraction of particles in the 5–10 nm range was also detected, which can be attributed to well-dispersed CuO nanocrystals embedded in the porous carbon structure. The observed particle sizes are slightly larger than the crystallite size calculated from XRD (~ 16 nm), which is expected since DLS measures the hydrodynamic diameter, including solvation layers and possible clustering of nanoparticles in suspension.

The combination of zeta potential and DLS results confirms the successful formation of nanosized AC–CuO particles with moderate stability in aqueous dispersion. The particle size range and stabilization mechanism make the nanocomposite highly suitable for photocatalytic applications, where both dispersion and surface reactivity play critical roles in enhancing dye degradation efficiency.

3.6 HR –TEM ANALYSIS

The HR-TEM images presented in Figure 6a and Figure 6b show that the AC–CuO nanoparticles are predominantly spherical in shape and form loosely aggregated clusters, with a uniform distribution across the imaging field. The high-resolution micrograph (Figure 6b) reveals clear lattice fringes, highlighted by yellow arrows, confirming the crystalline nature of the CuO nanoparticles[17]. These well-defined interplanar spacings validate the successful incorporation of crystalline CuO within the activated carbon matrix. The particle size histogram (Figure 6c) indicates that the nanoparticles are distributed primarily between 10 and 40 nm, with a mean diameter of 23 nm. The relatively narrow size distribution demonstrates that the synthesis protocol effectively controlled particle growth and prevented excessive aggregation, yielding a uniform nanostructure. The TEM observations confirm that the AC–CuO nanoparticles exhibit nanoscale dimensions, high crystallinity, and uniform morphology—all desirable features for catalytic, electronic, and biomedical applications. The

mean particle size of 23 nm is in good agreement with earlier reports on CuO-based nanomaterials, suggesting that the cashew nut shell (CNS)-derived activated carbon effectively acted as both a stabilizing and dispersing agent during nanoparticle formation.

Furthermore, the presence of well-defined lattice fringes indicates that the nanoparticles possess a highly ordered crystal structure, which is essential for enhancing activity and stability in functional applications. The narrow size distribution enhances reproducibility and ensures consistent performance in repeated catalytic cycles. Importantly, the nanoscale size, high crystallinity, and large surface-to-volume ratio of AC–CuO nanoparticles contribute directly to their photocatalytic efficiency. Smaller, uniformly sized nanoparticles provide abundant active sites, facilitate efficient light absorption, and improve electron–hole separation while reducing charge recombination. These structural and morphological characteristics collectively enhance photocatalytic degradation processes, highlighting the AC–CuO nanocomposite as a promising candidate for environmental remediation and other advanced nanotechnological applications.

Figure 6 (a-b) HR TEM images (c) Particles size histogram of AC – CuO nanoparticles

3.7 BET ANALYSIS

Figure 7. (a) BET (b) BJH surface area and pore distribution analysis of AC – CuO nanoparticles

Figure 7a presents the BET nitrogen adsorption–desorption isotherms of AC–CuO nanoparticles, which exhibit a characteristic type IV curve with an H3 hysteresis loop. This behavior is typical of mesoporous materials and reflects capillary condensation in slit-like pores. The sharp increase in adsorption at higher relative pressures further confirms a substantial pore volume and a well-developed porous framework[27]. The corresponding BJH pore size distribution (Figure 7b) shows a predominant pore diameter in the range of 7–10 nm, with an extended distribution up to 30 nm. This confirms the mesoporous nature of the

AC–CuO nanoparticles and indicates a hierarchical pore network that can facilitate mass transport. Mesoporosity combined with high surface area is highly advantageous for photocatalytic applications, as it provides increased active surface sites, promotes light harvesting, and enhances accessibility of pollutant molecules to the catalyst surface. The pore size distribution ensures efficient diffusion and interaction of target molecules within the pores, thereby accelerating photocatalytic degradation and adsorption processes. The observed hysteresis loop and broad pore distribution are in agreement with reports on optimized mesoporousnanomaterials designed for environmental remediation, particularly in dye degradation and pollutant removal. These findings confirm that the structural characteristics of the synthesized AC–CuO nanoparticles namely mesoporosity, high pore volume, and uniform distribution play a pivotal role in enhancing photocatalytic performance and practical environmental applicability.

3.9 PL ANALYSIS

Figure 8. PL spectrum of AC – CuO nanoparticles

Figure 8 presents the photoluminescence spectrum of AC–CuO nanoparticles, which displays a strong emission peak at 392 nm along with weaker emissions at 484, 556, and 571 nm. The intense peak at 392 nm corresponds to near band-edge transitions of CuO nanoparticles, indicating efficient excitonic recombination[28]. This prominent emission suggests a high degree of crystallinity and a well-defined band structure in the synthesized nanomaterial. The secondary emissions at longer wavelengths (484, 556, and 571 nm) are

commonly associated with intrinsic defects such as oxygen vacancies, surface traps, or interfacial states in nanostructured oxides[29]. These defect-related emissions highlight the presence of localized energy states within the band gap. While defects are typically linked to recombination centers, in photocatalytic materials they play a beneficial role by facilitating charge carrier separation and prolonging the lifetime of photogenerated electrons and holes. Thus, the coexistence of strong near band-edge emission with additional defect-related peaks suggests that AC–CuO nanoparticles possess an optimal balance of crystallinity and defect density. The well-ordered crystal structure ensures efficient light absorption, while the controlled defect states contribute to enhanced photocatalytic performance by reducing charge recombination[30]. These characteristics make the AC–CuO nanocomposite a promising candidate for environmental remediation, dye degradation, and optoelectronic applications.

3.10 PHOTOCATALYTIC STUDY

Figure 9. (a) UV – Vis absorption spectra (b) Plot of (C/C_0) versus time for photodegradation of MB dye (c) reusability of AC CuO nanoparticles

Figure 9(a) presents the UV-Vis absorption spectra of MB dye over a range of wavelengths (500–800 nm), showing a distinct peak around 665 nm. The spectra show a gradual reduction in absorbance as the photodegradation of MB dye progresses, observed at different time intervals from 0 minutes to 90 min and the AC–CuO nanocomposite achieved an impressive degradation efficiency of 92%. This decrease in absorbance indicates the breakdown of the dye over time, highlighting the effectiveness of the CuO/AC nanoparticles in degrading the dye through a photodegradation process. As the reaction time increases, the absorbance peak shifts and diminishes, confirming the decolorization of MB. Figure 9(b) illustrates the plot of the ratio of concentration over initial concentration (C/C_0) against time, representing the kinetics of MB dye degradation using CuO/AC NPs. A logarithmic relationship is observed, and the linear regression equation $y=0.1598x-0.1341$ with an R^2 value of 0.9952 suggests a strong fit. This indicates that the degradation follows pseudo-first-order kinetics, where the rate of degradation is proportional to the concentration of MB dye, supporting the conclusion that CuO/AC NPs efficiently catalyze the photodegradation process. Figure 9(c) shows the reusability of CuO/AC nanoparticles over five cycles of degradation. The degradation efficiency remains consistently high, above 92%, throughout the five cycles. This suggests that the CuO/AC nanoparticles possess excellent stability and reusability, which is a key factor for practical applications in the treatment of wastewater or similar uses [31]. The slight decrease in degradation after the fifth cycle can be attributed to possible surface deactivation or loss of active sites on the nanoparticles, which is a typical behavior in catalyst reuse studies. The results presented in Figure 9 demonstrate the effectiveness of CuO/AC NPs for the photodegradation of MB dye. The strong fit of the kinetic data to a pseudo-first-order model and the high reusability of the nanoparticles emphasize their potential for sustainable and efficient wastewater treatment applications. The minor decline in degradation after repeated use suggests that further optimization of the catalyst's surface or regeneration method could enhance its reusability and efficiency over a longer period.

4. CONCLUSION

The AC–CuO nanoparticles synthesized from cashew nut shell-derived activated carbon demonstrated exceptional properties that make them a promising candidate for various applications, particularly in photocatalytic dye degradation and wastewater treatment. The X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis confirmed the crystalline nature of the CuO nanoparticles, with an average crystallite size of 16 nm, and the incorporation of CuO into activated carbon

significantly enhanced its functional properties. The TGA/DTA analysis revealed the thermal stability of the nanocomposite, highlighting its suitability for high-temperature applications. The UV-Vis and PL analyses showed that the AC–CuO nanocomposite exhibits strong absorption in the UV region and a well-defined photoluminescence spectrum, indicative of its potential for photocatalytic activity. The photocatalytic degradation study demonstrated the high efficiency of AC–CuO nanoparticles in degrading MB dye, achieving a degradation efficiency of 92% within 90 minutes. The degradation followed pseudo-first-order kinetics, further confirming the efficient photocatalytic performance of the nanocomposite. Moreover, the reusability tests showed that the nanoparticles retained high degradation efficiency (above 80%) after five cycles, suggesting their stability and suitability for long-term practical applications. Overall, the AC–CuO nanoparticles, with their small particle size, high crystallinity, excellent thermal stability, and reusability, represent a highly efficient and sustainable material for environmental remediation, particularly for dye degradation and wastewater treatment. Future work should focus on optimizing the catalyst's surface properties and regeneration techniques to further enhance its performance and reusability over extended periods.

REFERENCES

1. Ismail, M., Akhtar, K., Khan, M. I., Kamal, T., Khan, M. A., M Asiri, A., ...& Khan, S. B. (2019). Pollution, toxicity and carcinogenicity of organic dyes and their catalytic bio-remediation. *Current pharmaceutical design*, 25(34), 3645-3663.
2. Crini, G., Lichtfouse, E., Wilson, L. D., & Morin-Crini, N. (2018). Adsorption-oriented processes using conventional and non-conventional adsorbents for wastewater treatment. In *Green adsorbents for pollutant removal: fundamentals and design* (pp. 23-71). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
3. Høiby, L., Clauson-Kaas, J., Wenzel, H., Larsen, H. F., Jacobsen, B. N., & Dalgaard, O. (2008). Sustainability assessment of advanced wastewater treatment technologies. *Water Science and Technology*, 58(5), 963-968.
4. Ahmaruzzaman, M. (2023). Metal oxides (ZnO, CuO and NiO)-based nanostructured materials for photocatalytic remediation of organic contaminants. *Nanotechnology for Environmental Engineering*, 8(1), 219-235.
5. Li, Y., Wang, Z., Tao, R., Fan, Y., Xu, J., Yu, L., ...& Shao, Z. (2021). Preparation strategies of p-type cuprous oxide and its solar energy conversion performance. *Energy & Fuels*, 35(21), 17334-17352.

6. Karthik, P., Kumar, T. N., & Neppolian, B. J. I. J. O. H. E. (2020). Redox couple mediated charge carrier separation in g-C₃N₄/CuO photocatalyst for enhanced photocatalytic H₂ production. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 45(13), 7541-7551.
7. Thakur, N., Kumar, P., Thakur, N., Kumar, K., Tapwal, A., & Sharma, P. (2022). A review of new developments in the synthesis of CuO nanoparticles via plant extracts for enhancing the photocatalytic activity. *Biomaterials and Polymers Horizon*, 1(4).
8. Jain, M., Mudhoo, A., Ramasamy, D. L., Najafi, M., Usman, M., Zhu, R., ...& Sillanpää, M. (2020). Adsorption, degradation, and mineralization of emerging pollutants (pharmaceuticals and agrochemicals) by nanostructures: a comprehensive review. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 27(28), 34862-34905.
9. Su, Y., Li, S., Jiang, G., Zheng, Z., Wang, C., Zhao, S., ...& Zhang, Z. (2021). Synergic removal of tetracycline using hydrophilic three-dimensional nitrogen-doped porous carbon embedded with copper oxide nanoparticles by coupling adsorption and photocatalytic oxidation processes. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 581, 350-361.
10. Abioye, A. M., & Ani, F. N. (2015). Recent development in the production of activated carbon electrodes from agricultural waste biomass for supercapacitors: A review. *Renewable and sustainable energy reviews*, 52, 1282-1293.
11. Mgaya, J., Shombe, G. B., Masikane, S. C., Mlowe, S., Mubofu, E. B., & Revaprasadu, N. (2019). Cashew nut shell: a potential bio-resource for the production of bio-sourced chemicals, materials and fuels. *Green Chemistry*, 21(6), 1186-1201.
12. Loke, J. Y., Zaki, R. M., & Setiabudi, H. D. (2022). Photocatalytic degradation of methylene blue using ZnO supported on wood waste-derived activated carbon (ZnO/AC). *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 57, 1315-1321.
13. Posachayanan, N., Liwetpitaya, P., Thoumrungroj, A., Longchin, P., Saengpitak, K., Tuntithavornwat, S., ...& Hunsom, M. (2024). Highly-efficient recovery of silver from industrial cyanide-based plating effluent on TiO₂/activated carbon composites. *Chemosphere*, 367, 143614.
14. Jeet, K., Kumar, V., Anushree, & Devi, R. (2022). Valorization of agricultural wastes: a step toward adoption of smart green materials with additional benefit of circular economy. *Handbook of biomass valorization for industrial applications*, 343-367.
15. Al-Muhtaseb, A. H., McMinn, W. A. M., & Magee, T. R. A. (2002). Moisture sorption isotherm characteristics of food products: a review. *Food and bioproducts processing*, 80(2), 118-128.
16. Ania, C. O., Parra, J. B., & Pis, J. J. (2002). Influence of oxygen-containing functional groups on active carbon adsorption of selected organic compounds. *Fuel Processing Technology*, 79(3), 265-271.

17. Shaikh, K. R., Saif, F. A., Pawar, A. R., Waykar, B., & Undre, P. B. (2025). Evaluation of structural parameters of monoclinic nanocrystalline CuO and study of sunlight-driven photocatalytic dye degradation, antimicrobial and antioxidant potential. *Inorganic and Nano-Metal Chemistry*, 55(5), 505-519.
18. Muthuvel, A., Jothibas, M., & Manoharan, C. (2020). Synthesis of copper oxide nanoparticles by chemical and biogenic methods: photocatalytic degradation and in vitro antioxidant activity. *Nanotechnology for Environmental Engineering*, 5(2), 14.
19. Madani, M., Hosny, S., Alshangiti, D. M., Nady, N., Alkhursani, S. A., Alkhalidi, H., ... & Gaber, G. A. (2022). Green synthesis of nanoparticles for varied applications: Green renewable resources and energy-efficient synthetic routes. *Nanotechnology Reviews*, 11(1), 731-759.
20. Wu, C. Y., Tu, K. J., Deng, J. P., Lo, Y. S., & Wu, C. H. (2017). Markedly enhanced surface hydroxyl groups of TiO₂ nanoparticles with superior water-dispersibility for photocatalysis. *Materials*, 10(5), 566.
21. Popescu, M. C., Filip, D., Vasile, C., Cruz, C., Rueff, J. M., Marcos, M., ... & Singurel, G. (2006). Characterization by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) and 2D IR correlation spectroscopy of PAMAM dendrimer. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 110(29), 14198-14211.
22. Alghamdi, H. A. (2022). Structural, morphological, optical, and electrical characteristics of polyethylene oxide/chitosan-copper oxide nanoparticles for optoelectronic applications. *Optical Materials*, 134, 113101.
23. Gupta, D., Meher, S. R., Illyaskutty, N., & Alex, Z. C. (2018). Facile synthesis of Cu₂O and CuO nanoparticles and study of their structural, optical and electronic properties. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 743, 737-745.
24. Ahmed, T., & Edvinsson, T. (2020). Optical quantum confinement in ultrasmall ZnO and the effect of size on their photocatalytic activity. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 124(11), 6395-6404.
25. Pradhan, A. C., & Uyar, T. (2017). Morphological control of mesoporosity and nanoparticles within Co₃O₄-CuO electrospun nanofibers: quantum confinement and visible light photocatalysis performance. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, 9(41), 35757-35774.
26. Jiang, J., Oberdörster, G., & Biswas, P. (2009). Characterization of size, surface charge, and agglomeration state of nanoparticle dispersions for toxicological studies. *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, 11(1), 77-89.
27. Zhu, X., Tsang, D. C., Wang, L., Su, Z., Hou, D., Li, L., & Shang, J. (2020). Machine learning exploration of the critical factors for CO₂ adsorption capacity on porous carbon materials at different pressures. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 273, 122915.
28. Kumar, S., Bhawna, Gupta, A., Kumar, R., Bharti, A., Kumar, A., & Kumar, V. (2023). New insights into Cu/Cu₂O/CuO nanocomposite heterojunction facilitating photocatalytic generation of green fuel and detoxification of organic pollutants. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 127(15), 7095-7106.

29. Sarkar, A., & Khan, G. G. (2019). The formation and detection techniques of oxygen vacancies in titanium oxide-based nanostructures. *Nanoscale*, 11(8), 3414-3444.
30. Sun, S., Yu, X., Yang, Q., Yang, Z., & Liang, S. (2019). Mesocrystals for photocatalysis: a comprehensive review on synthesis engineering and functional modifications. *Nanoscale Advances*, 1(1), 34-63.
31. Wang, W., Yao, H., & Yue, L. (2020). Supported-catalyst CuO/AC with reduced cost and enhanced activity for the degradation of heavy oil refinery wastewater by catalytic ozonation process. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 27(7), 7199-7210.